

MSCA and Citizens 2023 - **Events 2025** - QUESTIONNAIRE

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA)

REA.A - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions & Support to Experts
A.4 - MSCA and citizens, COFUND, Global Postdoctoral Fellowships

Questionnaire on the European Researchers' Night - 2025 Edition and the Researchers at Schools activities carried out up to this date

*** 1. Acronym of the project**

EU-EMBRACES

*** 2. Country of the event**

Portugal

*** 3. Location/s**

Alcanena, Braga, Bragança, Estremoz, Lagos, Lisboa, Vila Nova de Foz Côa, Oeiras, Porto

*** 4. Number of cities in which the event took place**

9

*** 5. Type of event**

Full online

- Onsite
- Mix of online and onsite

6. In case it is a mix online-onsite give the approximate % of online and onsite activities:

AWARENESS CAMPAIGN

Which have been the most efficient actions in terms of reaching out to the target audiences?

7. Promotional material

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Folders
- Brochures
- Programmes
- Leaflets
- Posters
- Citylights
- Billboards
- Promotional video
- Advertisement in public spaces (squares, places, streets,...)
- Advertising on Radio - National
- Advertising on Radio - Local
- Advertising on TV - National
- Advertising on TV - Local
- Written media - Newspapers/Magazines
- Written media - Newsletters
- Written media - Other
- Written media at national level
- Written media at regional level

8. Project Website

- National
- Regional/local
- Links with other national or European websites

9. Social networks

- Facebook
- Twitter
- Flickr
- Instagram
- TikTok
- Other

10. Press conference(s)

- At national level
- At regional/local level
- With other projects from the same country (if relevant)

Please keep a sample of the promotional material (posters, leaflets, programmes, gadgets...) You do not have to send it to us, unless you are requested to do so by your Project Officer.

RESEARCHERS AT SCHOOLS ACTIVITIES (online or onsite)

11. In the framework of your MSCA and Citizens project, have you organised Researchers at Schools Activities?

- Yes
- No

If "No" move to question 21, 'PRE-EVENTS' Section

If "Yes", please answer the following questions:

12. Type of event

- Full online
- Onsite
- Mix of online and onsite

13. How researchers at school activities have been organised?

219

14. Which type of schools:

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Primary
- Secondary
- Other

If other (please specify)

15. (Approximately) how many students/pupils have been reached?

16. What kind of activities were offered:

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Oral presentation
- Research collaborations
- Talks
- Hand-on experiments
- Questions and answers session
- Workshops
- Games
- Science kit for schools
- Marketplace activities
- Research seminars
- Science hacks
- Other

If other activities (please specify)

17. Area of activities:

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Chemistry
- Social Sciences and Humanities
- Economic Sciences
- Information Science and Engineering
- Environment and Geosciences
- Life Sciences
- Mathematics
- Physics
- Covid-19
- Other

If other area of activities (please specify)

18. Overall, how many researchers participated?

279

19. In the case that MSCA researchers were involved, how many participated?

20. Suggestions for the European Commission to improve the Researchers at Schools activities

Comments

We currently lack the ability to directly target researchers who benefit from MSCA funding and participated in the Researchers at Schools activities. This poses a challenge if maximizing the involvement of these researchers is a key objective for the European Commission. Nevertheless, we did our best to mitigate this limitation for researchers participating in ERNs.

PRE-EVENT(S)

21. How many pre-events have you organised?

31

If "0" move question 27 in the section 'Activities during the NIGHT'

22. What was the (typical) duration of a pre-event? (Number of days - If halfday encode 0.5)

1

23. What was the period when those pre-events were organised?

From

15/03/2025

To

22/09/2025

24. What was the nature of the pre-events:

- Online
- Onsite
- Hybrid (simultaneous onsite and online participation)

25. What kind of activities were offered during those pre-events:

- Hands-on activities and demonstrations
- Workshops
- Science shows
- Quizzes, escape rooms and challenges
- Informal talks, Q&A with researchers
- Games
- Open days and guided tours
- Theatre
- Other

Other pre-event(s) (please specify)

yoga session, walking & trekking, bioblitz, exposition, energy-generating cycling

26. Type of Pre-event

- Flashmobs
- Teasing events in public places
- Teasing events at partners' premises
- Other

If other type of activities proposed during pre-event(s) (please specify)

expositions, yoga session, walking & trekking

ACTIVITIES DURING THE NIGHT

27. Type of activities organised

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Hands-on activities
- Workshops
- Exhibitions
- Science shows
- Demonstrations
- Competitions
- Quizzes
- Informal talks/written chats, or Q&A with researchers
- Games
- Theatre
- Virtual Guided tours
- Other

Other (please specify)

Musical concerts, Molecular gastronomy, Escape rooms, video art, local product testing

28. Which were the most successful activities from a qualitative perspective? Please specify what were the topics addressed in these activities.

- Hands-on activities
- Workshops
- Exhibitions
- Science shows
- Demonstrations
- Competitions
- Quizzes
- Informal talks/written chats, or Q&A with researchers
- Games
- Theatre
- Virtual Guided tours

Please specify which topic/s for each of the activities ticked above:

1) Hands-on Activities topics: Laboratory sciences, robotics and engineering, sustainability and food science, sensory science, environment - Laboratory and scientific experiments: Microscopy, observation of zooplankton, blood, corals, insects, DNA extraction, and chemistry demonstrations such as elephant toothpaste, coconut foam, sunscreen formulation. - Robotics and engineering: Human gyroscope, robot demonstrations, welding activities, drones, electronic circuits, and smart fibre technologies. - Scientific cooking and sustainability: Seaweed rice, molecular gastronomy, honey tasting, hydroponics, Mediterranean diet, and edible insects. - Sensorial activities: Olive oil analysis, aroma identification, tasting experiences. - Scientific crafts and maker workshops: DNA bracelets, rockets, and experiments with non-Newtonian fluids. - Field or outdoor activities: Yoga, breathing exercises, and environmental observation. 2) Informal Talks / Q&A with Researchers Main

topics: Biomedical sciences, environmental studies, health innovation, and scientific careers. Examples of activities: - Slow dating and science cafés: Informal discussions with scientists on topics such as cancer research, environmental challenges, and biomedicine. - Thematic discussions: Cancer and novel therapies, climate change, healthy eating, and innovation in health. - Sharing scientific journeys: Researchers present their personal and professional paths, encouraging open dialogue and curiosity. 3) Quizzes Main topics: General science, biomedicine, sensory science, and scientific curiosity. Examples of activities: - "What is this?": Identification game using scientific objects or concepts. - "Who Wants to Be a Scientist?": a quiz format inspired by "Who Wants to Be a Millionaire?", focused on science knowledge. - Aroma challenges and riddles: Sensory-based guessing and learning activities. - Health and biomedicine quizzes: Interactive questions to test knowledge in these areas.

RESEARCHERS INVOLVED

29. Total number of researchers involved in the activities organised

30. Number of researchers involved having benefitted from Marie Skłodowska-Curie schemes

31. Number of researchers involved having benefitted from EU support (FP7, H2020, HE) other than MSCA

ATTENDANCE AND OUTREACH

32. Overall number of attendees (whether possible, distributed by location)

33. Estimate number of people made aware of the European Researchers' Night and its objectives

34. If applicable, how did users rate the onsite experience?

- Very positive
- Positive
- Neutral
- Negative
- Very negative

35. What were the most usual feedbacks of the attendees/users about the onsite experience?

Feedback from participants highlights the diversity of topics and activities as one of the main strengths of the European Researchers' Night. Visitors appreciated the opportunity to explore different areas of science in a single event, appealing to audiences of all ages. They also valued the direct interaction with researchers, noting the open and informal exchanges that made learning more engaging. Many comments praised the clarity of explanations and the hands-on activities, which helped turn scientific concepts into concrete experiences. Participants frequently mentioned the smooth organisation and the welcoming atmosphere, which contributed to a positive and accessible experience for everyone. Regarding areas for improvement, the most common suggestions concerned the limited space due to high attendance, the desire for a longer or multi-day event, and the need for greater outreach and promotion within the community.

36. If applicable, how did users rate the online experience?

- Very positive
- Positive
- Neutral
- Negative
- Very negative

37. What were the most usual feedbacks of the attendees/users about the online experience?

COOPERATION WITH OTHER FUNDED PROJECTS

38. Cooperation with projects in your country

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify the acronym of these projects or number

39. Cooperation with projects in another (others) country(ies)

- Yes
- No

If yes, which projects in which country(ies)

ESCIENCIA (RESEARCH NIGHT: BRINGING RESEARCHERS INTO THE LIGHT) in Spain

40. Which type of cooperation?

- Awareness
- Common activities
- Exchange of researchers
- Real time connections
- Impact assessment
- Other

If other type of cooperation (please specify)

Please elaborate briefly on what was done in terms on cooperation

We met with the RESEARCH NIGHT: BRINGING RESEARCHERS INTO THE LIGHT project to exchange ideas and experiences on event organization and dissemination strategies. Both consortia agreed to collaborate on awareness campaigns by cross-promoting each other's events on social media. However, because the follow-up took place too close to the event date, we were unable to implement specific joint activities.

41. Have you involved the Marie Curie Alumni Association in your project activities?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was their role?

COMMENTS

42. Specific difficulties encountered and solutions identified

Comments

The ERN has now become a large-scale event with significant visibility and high expectations from both participants and the research institutions involved - a result that reflects the success and commitment of all the organizing consortia. However, the increasing size and scope of the project now require resources that go beyond the financial support provided by the project itself and our current capacity. This represents a key challenge we have been addressing by seeking additional sources of funding and collaboration, including partnerships with municipalities and private sponsors, as well as the active involvement of a large number of volunteers. It is important to emphasize that the EU funding remains absolutely essential as the foundational support that enables us to leverage these additional resources and partnerships; without this core funding, mobilizing the necessary supplementary support would not be possible.

43. Aspects you would intend to modify during future editions

Comments

The involvement of multiple consortia and associated institutions organizing simultaneous Researchers' Night events, each with distinct visual identities, communication channels, and websites, has sometimes resulted in fragmented outreach particularly in regions hosting more than one event. For future editions, we aim to foster greater coordination among consortia by encouraging cross-linking and mutual references on their respective websites.

44. Suggestions for the European Commission with a view to future calls

Comments

Based on our experience and impact analysis, we have observed that activities carried out throughout the year - particularly those involving schools, associations, and local communities- tend to be far more effective in engaging audiences who are generally more distant from science and scientists. By contrast, the audiences attending the European Researchers' Night events themselves usually have a higher-than-average cultural background and stronger pre-existing links with the scientific community (as students, researchers, or relatives of scientists). Our experience suggests that this gap can be mitigated through continuous, long-term engagement efforts that take place well before the Night itself, focusing on the inclusion of less-connected communities. For this reason, we believe that future calls should increasingly support projects that frame the European Researchers' Night not as a single, stand-alone event, but as the culmination of a year-long programme of outreach and engagement.

45. Any other issue that you would like to highlight

Thank you!

MSCA and Citizens Team

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Contact

[Contact Form](#)